

Determination of Temperature Coefficient of Palladium Catalyst on Alumina Support

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STUDIES on oxidation of methane and other hydrocarbon on palladium surface by micro calorimetric bead technique have been widely reported^{1,2}. Almost in every method, employed for study of kinetics using catalytic bead, temperature of catalytic surface has been directly measured or estimated using standard equation of platinum resistance thermometer^{2,3}. No attempt has been made to evaluate the temperature coefficient of calorimetric bead of palladium catalyst on alumina support. In the present study the same has been determined using standard equation, the value so determined was found to be varying with that for platinum, employed as a coil.

Experimental

The preparation of microcalorimetric bead (2-3 mm in length) used for the catalytic studies has been described by authors⁵ and other workers⁴. Other experimental arrangement for determination of temperature coefficient of bead has been shown in Fig. 1. For lower temperature ranges the bead

Fig. 1

terminals were soldered to 30 SWG copper wire and for higher temperature range contact arrangements were made. The copper terminals for bead and compensator were embedded in a asbestos plug to ensure rigidity, kept in a glass furnace having volume 500 ml and with a provision for heating up to 500°. The temperature of the furnace was controlled by Sunvic temperature controller, the temperature variation were recorded by precision thermometer. Resistances were measured with a Resistance Bridge.

Results and Discussion

Measurement of resistances with temperature variation for (a) platinum coil, (b) an alumina bead, (c) palladium coated bead of alumina were made at every 10° and 20° rise and at each temperature; average of ten readings were taken.

Using standard equation the values of temperature coefficient for three different materials were calculated between 40° and 50° and found to be .0028, .00169, .0024 respectively for platinum coil, alumina bead and palladium coated alumina bead. Values of temperature coefficient when calculated for wider range of temperature did not have very good agreement with measurement at lower temperature. This could be due to fluctuations in temperature at higher temperature.

With values so determined for temperature coefficients one can easily evaluate the surface temperature of such microcatalytic bead. Further attempt is being made to co-relate experimentally the temperature calculated from coefficient values and with those determined by I.R. and thermo-couple technique.

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Physico-chemical Properties of Magnesium Soaps of Lower Fatty Acids in Alcohols

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MAGNESIUM soaps find frequent use in greases¹⁻⁴, paints and varnishes⁵, catalytic actions⁶⁻⁸, etc. Their applications make it so important that it attracted the attention to study the properties in various solvents. Recently the behaviour of magnesium soaps of lower fatty acids in water has been-